

Speaking skills strategies for college ESL learners

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Abstract

Many people believe that knowing a language is similar to being able to speak it, and as a result, they perceive learning a language as understanding how to speak it. This study identifies the challenges in teaching speaking in English as a Second Language (ESL) classes and explains how ESL English teachers teach speaking to the students. A total of five (5) English teachers took part in the study. Through a series of interviews, the study explores the strategies in teaching speaking to the Filipino students and the challenges that they face while enhancing the proficiency of the students in speaking during their classroom activities. The study revealed that according to the teachers, Filipino tertiary students or ESL learners lack confidence in speaking, because they are intimidated by the fear of producing mistakes in pronunciation, grammar or vocabulary while speaking. Nonetheless, some ESL teachers have already developed strategies on how to deal with the challenges in teaching speaking. The study further recommended that teachers should promote the use of the English language through institutionalized programs like the Speak English Movement.

Keywords: *Speaking skills strategies; English as a Second Language; College learners.*

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Introduction

Many people believe that knowing a language is similar to being able to speak it, and as a result, they perceive learning a language as understanding how to speak it. According to Nunan (1991), success is determined by his or her capacity to hold conversations in the target language. Therefore, students can quickly lose their passion for learning and feel discouraged if they do not acquire the ability to speak or do not have any opportunities to do so in the language classroom. However, it can be argued that if proper strategies are applied in conducting proper activities, speaking during lectures can be a lot of fun, increasing overall learner motivation and fostering a lively environment in the English language classroom.

Teaching speaking skills has been considered a “burdensome task” for many ESL teachers due to several factors, such as class size, student anxiety, limited turn-taking activities, and the non-specific approaches used to teach speaking (Bygate, 2001). At times, there is a tendency to focus on reading and writing rather than the major macro-skills an ESL student should engage in (Hamid et al., 2013). Lazaraton (2014), however, states that “the act of speaking is staggeringly complex,” which makes it one of the most perplexing of the traditional four skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing to teach and assess, which is also the main reason teaching speaking in ESL classes is sometimes not given more time and emphasis. In addition, most speaking activities are lighthearted and very informal, even if the concepts being discussed are content-based or gathered from other academic subjects, with ESL teachers relegating the more “serious” questions to writing activities. Goh and Burns (2012) suggest that teachers should be aware of what the relevant areas are in teaching speaking in order to incorporate “teach speaking” into the curriculum and not just “do the speaking” with the students.

Even Bygate (1998) believes that speaking is, in many ways, an undervalued skill and a rapid activity. We practically all speak, so perhaps we take this capacity for granted too much. Speaking is frequently viewed as a "popular" method of expression that uses the less-regarded "colloquial" register; reading abilities are generally regarded as being more valuable. Being aware that speaking is temporary and spontaneous and might consequently be perceived as simple, superficial, or glib may also contribute to this relative neglect. Bygate (2001) further emphasizes that speaking is a rapid activity, and to be successful in it "depends on automation."

Furthermore, to learn how to speak in a second language competently requires a student to adjust to complex and fast transferring of ideas, which results in the student undergoing "a high element of doing various things at the same time" (Johnson & Golombek, 2020). ESL students must combine various skills, knowledge, and processes, which include production as well as generating responses once they are questioned. These responses should be relevant, appropriate, and comprehensible in order for ESL students to be considered competent second-language speakers of English. They must also be very good listeners who are ready to engage in the various discourses competent speakers have to engage in (Ellis & Shintani, 2014).

That is why the concept of teaching speaking is about teaching how to use the language for communication, feeling or thinking about other people, or transferring ideas. River (1978) states that speaking arises from the first interaction with the language that is learned, because by speaking, we can transfer our ideas or thoughts to other people. Moreover, Johnson (2009) says that the essence of human language is human activity on the part of the individual to make him understand another, and activity on the part of the other understands what was on the first. Then, he adds that languages are an activity that permits people to communicate with each other. So it is clear that language is very important. Not only can we teach exactly what will be said, but also how to cope with certain situations. By placing the pupils in scenarios where the issue is being discussed, the teacher teaches speaking. Students must be fluent in the subject because they will need to describe it orally using their knowledge of the subject.

In the Philippines, it was inevitable to acquire a second language as history dictated it. Colonization has brought into contact with foreign cultures that have an interest in the language the natives used. Existing studies back up the claim that a considerable number of people in the world have received instruction in at least one foreign language (Arriola, 2002). In fact, the majority of the population of the Philippines speaks English at least somewhat fluently, making them one of the most English-speaking countries in the world. More than 14 million Filipinos speak English, which has traditionally been one of the nation's official spoken languages. It serves as the major language of teaching in educational institutions and the language of trade and law (Cabigon, 2015).

Cabigon also stated that English language proficiency is another one of the nation's assets that has boosted the economy and has made the Philippines the world's top location for contact centers, surpassing India in 2012. Analysts express the fact that Filipinos have a more neutral accent, which is one of the major factors in this overtake (Chavez, 2014). However, in an assembly organized by the British Council, key stakeholders from the academic, private, government, and non-government sectors recognized the fact that even if the Philippines is good in terms of English proficiency, there have been questions about how much of a competitive edge the nation still has. Everyone involved acknowledged that the nation must increase its efforts to improve English education and learning, particularly speaking, to make it a necessary skill for the workforce. This is an initiative that could potentially strengthen the Philippines' distinct advantage in this part of the world, particularly with the upcoming ASEAN economic integration (Cabigon, 2015).

Despite this recognition, however, there are reports that also show a decline in the ability of Filipinos to speak, especially the English language. Even as the commercial value of the lingua franca has increased, the Philippines, where commonly used English was previously an official language, has seen a collective proficiency decline over the years. According to a study by Hopkins International Partners, Filipino university graduates' average scores in the Test of English for International Communication

(TOEIC) were “lower than the competency requirement for taxi drivers in Dubai and United Arab Emirates” (Leonen, 2018).

Indeed, teaching speaking in the Philippines shows difficulties and crises. Aside from the problems of pedagogy, certain issues have to do with economic and policy concerns. Otones (1988) in her article “*The State of English Language Teaching in Educational System Today*,” says that the problems that were prevalent in the 1950s still persist to this day. Otones referred to the report made by Prator (1950) regarding the crises confronting language teaching at the time his study was published. The study reported the following concerns:

- Great decrease in the length of the daily school session
- Decrease in the number of years of instruction
- Transfer to national language the time formerly spend in using English
- Decreased supply of texts and supplementary readings
- Increased proportion of untrained teaches
- Larger classes
- Deterioration of language models
- Uncertainty as to position of English and loss of teacher morale

With this study, the researcher hopes to revisit the condition of the proficiency of the Filipinos in speaking the English language, particularly the college students, and recall the challenges that the students and even the teachers face in the teaching of speaking to be able to learn the proper strategies that will eventually address the need to enhance the speaking skills of the Filipinos.

Theoretical Basis

There is no one better to talk about theories that involve the teaching of speaking skills than the theory of language learning. Language learning theories have been discussed for as long as one cares to remember. It may be surprising to know that the problems that philosophers in ancient Greece and 16th-century France were concerned about are largely still relevant today.

The goal of teaching speaking or using the language orally is to develop what Hymes (1972) referred to as “communicative competence.” This phrase was created by Hymes to contrast Chomsky’s theory of competence with a communicative perspective of language. Chomsky held that linguistic theory is concerned primarily with an ideal speaker-listener in a completely homogeneous speech community who knows its language perfectly and is unaffected by such grammatically irrelevant conditions as memory limitation, distractions, shifts of attention and interest, and errors (random or characteristic) in applying his knowledge of the language in actual performance (Chomsky, 2006).

Hymes’ theory of communicative competence was a definition of what a speaker needs to know in order to be communicatively competent in a speech community. In Hymes’ view, a person who acquires communicative competence acquires both knowledge and ability for language use with respect to:

1. whether (and to what degree) something is formally possible;
2. whether (and to what degree) something is feasible in virtue of the means of implementation available;
3. whether (and to what degree) something is appropriate (adequate, happy, successful) in relation to a context in which it is used and evaluated;
4. whether (and to what degree) something is in fact done, actually performed, and what doing entails.

Conduit in the theory of communicative competence is a model by Savignon (2018), who puts a much greater emphasis on the aspect of ability in her concept of communicative competence (as cited by Astudillo, 2019). Savignon described communicative competence as “the ability to function in a truly

communicative setting—that is, in a dynamic exchange in which linguistic competence must adapt itself to the total informational input, both linguistic and paralinguistic, of one or more interlocutors” (Savignon, 2018). According to her and many other theoreticians (e.g., Canale & Swain, 1980; Skehan, 1996, 1998; Bachman & Palmer, 1996), the nature of communicative competence is not static but dynamic; it is more interpersonal than intrapersonal and relative rather than absolute. Context also has a key role in defining it. Savignon defined competence as a fundamental ability and performance as an outward display of competence when describing the difference between the two. She feels that performance is the only way for competence to be seen, developed, maintained, and evaluated.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

The study explores the strategies for teaching speaking to Filipinos as reflected in the interview with the English professors and also the challenges that they face while enhancing the proficiency of the students in speaking. Determining the strategies for teaching speaking to non-native speakers would not be possible without considering the following:

Speaking. It is a cooperative procedure that includes information production, information reception, and information processing. It requires that students grasp when, why, and how to produce language in addition to knowing how to express specific language features like pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary (Burns & Joyce, 1997).

Teaching Strategy. These are the techniques adopted to assist students in learning the desired course material so that they can create attainable objectives in the future. To create the best approach to dealing with the chosen target population, teaching strategies examine the various accessible learning modalities.

Non-Native Speaker. In this study, it refers to the Filipino tertiary students, whose native tongue is not English. Although the Filipinos were colonized by the Americans, who are native speakers of English, they still experience challenges in speaking English, so they must be guided on the proper strategies to cope with the use of standard English and always be prepared in today’s globalized world language.

Statement of the Problem

With the new Commission on Higher Education (CHED) curriculum, which includes purposeful communication as its general education subject, this qualitative study can strongly shape how English

language speaking skills should be implemented at the tertiary level of ESL learners in the Philippine setting. However, in order to achieve these approaches and strategies in teaching speaking, the challenges in teaching the second language should first be determined.

As such, for this study, the following are the specific research questions:

1. What are the challenges in teaching speaking in ESL classes?
2. How do ESL English teachers teach speaking?

Scope and Delimitation

The study refers to the Filipino students, particularly the tertiary students, as non-native speakers of English. These tertiary students experience difficulty speaking the English language, and these are what the English professors observe while teaching them. The ESL classes refer to the English classes in the Philippines, with the ESL teachers being the Filipino English teachers who teach the Filipino students English as a Second Language. With this study, the researcher hopes to address the problem by first identifying the challenges that the English professors face and giving a proper recommendation.

Methodology

Research Design

The design of the study is a qualitative one. Qualitative methods generally fall into five categories: basic qualitative study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, and case study. For a qualitative research study, selecting a study design that correlates with the question is imperative. Several types of qualitative research designs are used as fundamental frameworks to conduct studies. Individuals' lived experiences may become a phenomenon, and phenomenologists focus on participants' shared experiences as they gather data and individual experiences of a phenomenon to create a general description that includes all people's observations (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Another form commonly used in qualitative research, which was used in this study, is a case study, which is an in-depth study of a group, community, person, or event (Laws & McLeod, 2004).

Procedure

The study observed a systematic approach of analysis, by following the four different phases:

Phase I: Construct and validate the interview questions.

Phase II: Interview the ESL teachers.

Phase III: Transcribe the recorded interview.

Phase IV: Analyze the data.

Phase I. The researcher started by constructing an interview question to get the story behind the participants' experiences in dealing with the challenges that they face in teaching speaking to non-native speakers. Since the study focuses only on two research problems, the participants were asked two important questions about the challenges that they face in teaching speaking with non-native speakers and the teaching methodology or strategies that they use to address the needs of the students. The research questions were then validated by experts in the field of teaching speaking. Warm-up questions were also given before the start of the interview. At times, the participant is subjected to more free-form and participatory questioning from the researcher (Pe-Pua & Protacio-Marcelino, 2000). Although two lead questions were given, which

directly refer to the topic being studied, some questions were asked based on the participants' prior responses.

Phase II. Bernard (2017) states that data gathering plays a vital role in any research for the reason that the data will contribute to a better understanding of the study. The interviewees were purposefully selected using typical-case sampling. Since the study aims to identify strategies for teaching speaking to non-native speakers of English, the researcher purposefully interviewed five (5) college English professors in the substantive area. The college English professors, because of their expertise and experiences, were chosen and asked about their perspectives on the teaching of speaking, hence a good starting point for a qualitative method. Interview sessions consisted of semi-structured interviews with both open-ended and closed questions to gather data for this study. All the interview sessions were recorded through notetaking, accompanied by better listening and writing skills.

Phase III. The notes recorded from the interview were then transcribed to ensure the preservation of the data for further and better analysis. Through notetaking, the researcher was able to demonstrate a "stronger conceptual understanding and was more successful in applying and integrating the material compared to those who took notes with their laptops" (Roller, 2017). The recorded notes were encoded verbatim, which is frequently used in research as a data management method and is usually regarded as essential to the analysis as well as the interpretation of the data itself (Halcomb & Davidson, 2006).

Phase IV. Credible qualitative research requires data analysis to be conducted. It is frequently stated in qualitative research that the researcher's capacity to comprehend, articulate, and evaluate experiences and perspectives serves as the research instrument (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). In analyzing the responses of the participants, the researcher employed a thematic analysis, in which finding patterns or themes in qualitative data is what this approach comprises (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Braun and Clarke gave the following steps, which may not be necessarily linear. When dealing with complex data, the researcher frequently switches between them, possibly even many times.

Step 1: Become familiar with the data. The researcher re-read the transcript and extracted the important concepts needed for the study.

Step 2: General initial codes. After Step 1, the researcher had some initial thoughts on codes. The researcher worked through each transcript, coding every part of the text that seemed to specifically address the research questions. The codes were then compared and altered before the remainder of the transcript was started. The researcher went through printed copies of the transcripts using pens and highlighters, doing this manually or by hand.

Step 3: Search for themes. The researcher now looks for patterns that reflect anything important or fascinating about the research issue. Since the study only gathered small amounts of data from a small number of participants, the process of identifying preliminary topics and the coding stage have a lot in common. When the researcher looked at the codes in this instance, some of them obviously made up a theme.

Step 4: Review themes. The researcher updated and expanded the initial themes found in the third step's analysis. Since all the data make sense, the researcher gathered together all relevant data for each theme. This was done through a 'cut and paste' function in Microsoft Word processing.

Step 5: Define themes. The themes are now through their final round of revision, and the goal now is to find the core idea behind each theme (Clarke & Braun, 2018).

Step 6: Write-up. This is the output of the research, which is explained further in the last chapters of the paper.

Results and Discussion

Research Question No. 1. What are the challenges in teaching speaking in ESL classes?

The findings are presented in the form of codes or themes. As the participants shared the challenges of teaching speaking in an English class, they also needed to grapple with the challenges of their own external environment.

Theme 1: Difficulty in Pronouncing English Words Properly

The difficulty in pronouncing words was believed to be because English is not the mother tongue of Filipinos resulting to having a hard tongue as what T2 expressed, *“most of them, because I always believe that in speaking the English language since it’s not their mother tongue it’s a gift, with some Filipino students the local students, all of them are not ‘malambot ang dila’ (confident) in speaking. Even I have pronunciation drills, one on one pronunciation drills, they still have a hard time especially pronouncing words with th, f, [and] v, maybe because we don’t have those words in Tagalog.”* Similarly, T1 observed that most students produce sounds of English words incorrectly. Despite this T5 believes that pronunciation are also difficult for them, but these areas can be easily corrected and learned.

Theme 2: Limited Vocabulary Resulting to Code Switching

It has been an observation that most Filipinos do not usually read English materials, so their English vocabulary is limited resulting to translation from Tagalog to English. T2 believed that the main problem is limited vocabulary as she said, *“I observed that students shift to Tagalog although they ask permission if they can speak in Tagalog.”* T5 said that we always encourage students not to use Taglish, but it would be too hard for them. They would get frustrated because they have limited vocabulary in English. Mainly, vocabulary (or what English words to use) is the main problem.

Also, T5 observed that usually students had difficult conveying their thoughts in spoken English, they had problems explaining in pure English and would use Taglish instead. As a result, T4 observed that students lack vocabulary, so they have the tendency to form their ideas in Filipino and translate literally into English and T2 said that students tend to speak Tagalog halfway or Filipino so like some of the things are lost in translation.

However, T1 expressed that this habit of translation is not supposed to be allowed in a teaching speaking classes as she said students have difficulty in thinking of the English words, most often translate some English words into Tagalog. This is not supposed to be allowed in teaching speaking because students would get used in doing it and would not help them in learning the second language easily.

Theme 3: Lack of Confidence Caused by Fear of Mistakes

It has been a common observation that most tertiary students lack confidence in speaking English caused by their fear of producing mistakes in grammar or pronunciation. T4 observed that the main problem of the students is their shyness. T4 said, *“Most of my students don’t want to express themselves in English in fear of being ridiculed if they make a mistake.”* Even T2 said that most students lack confidence. *“Students hesitate in using the language; they even tell me they will be teased because of it just by using the English language. Students are very conscious in grammar that’s one of the problems, that’s why they hesitate in using the English language,”* the teacher added.

This is also an observation of T1 when she said that most of the students are intimidated by the fear of producing mistakes in grammar and pronunciation or not being able to express ideas in English. The same intimidation that T2 observed that when teachers talk to students in English, they are intimidated and that is why they do not answer back in English. Because of lack of confidence, as a result, T5 observed that as a result, they would hesitate to recite in class.

Theme 4: Millennial Behavior

Because of the effect of globalization and popular culture, most students just like any other students in different schools, they are dependent in the technology, especially in the use of gadgets resulting to the emergence of different behavior. This is evident when T3 observed that many of our students lack some ability to communicate. *“Because let’s face it. Most of the young ones are ‘glued into their smartphones,’ so one of the leading challenges in teaching speaking is that first of all, we lost the ability to speak with each other face to face, most of us communicate through the new media,”* the teacher explained.

This observation is indeed true in today’s generation. As a result of being exposed to different opinions posted in the social media, the tertiary students, who are mostly millennials, also developed different opinion towards the use of speaking in English, as what T1 observed. T1 said, *“I think the most difficult problem to deal with is that most students don’t even want to try speaking in English, not because they fear of the mistakes, but because on the first hand, they don’t even have the interest in the English language, fueled by their opinion that they are Filipinos anyway so why speak in English.”*

Research Question No. 2: How do ESL teachers teach speaking?

Theme 1: Encourage Students to Speak English

Most of the participants as ESL teacher agree that encouraging students to speak in English is their responsibility to help them develop their English skills. T3 said, *“I encourage students to speak English while inside the class. I keep on reminding them that having accent is not the basis for perfect or having the perfect grammar for as long as you can communicate what you want to say, and grammar can follow afterwards.”*

T1 encouraged students to speak by motivating students to speak by telling them that in speaking, errors are allowed compared to writing. Nobody should be criticized for speaking ungrammatically. In that way, students will not feel intimidated to speak. The teacher noted, *“I tell them that since it is a language class, everybody is encouraged to use the language. They are even allowed to chat about things that they are interested about, so noise is allowed. Only, they should do this using the English language. By saying that, it’s either that students feel challenged to speak in English so you will expect to hear noises. But noise is okay, at least, the students are speaking in English. Noise is allowed because anyway it’s a language class. Everybody is encouraged to use the language. Or students will keep quiet and do not say anything anymore. But it’s also okay; at least the class is quiet.”*

The same encouragement is observed on the part of T3 when he said, *“I ask them to speak in English and then I keep on reminding them that having an accent is not the basis for perfect or having the perfect grammar for as long as you can communicate what you want to say, and grammar can follow afterward.”*

However, T2 also believes that we should encourage our students to be more confident in using the English language. *“I think the confidence of our students should be, we should encourage our students to be more confident in using the English language, I tell them it’s because we Filipinos are very grammar conscious. I encourage students to talk in English especially when they have just arrived in the country. Just like in this class, we have student from Jordan, so whether they like it or not, they should speak in English because of course that is also respect for the foreigner students,”* the teacher stated.

Theme 2: Teaching Speaking by Modelling

Indeed, teachers are the best models. In teaching speaking, The participants, as the ESL teachers become role models to students by demonstrating themselves how to speak in English. T4 is even a good example when she specifically explained, *“I follow an outline, which includes recognition and production activities. First, I introduce to them the English sound system, covering vowels, consonants, and diphthongs, including suprasegmentals. I use videos when available, for them to be able to listen to native*

speakers. When they are already familiar with the sounds, I test their recognitions by making them identify similar and dissimilar sounds. Then, I give them production activities wherein I asked them to produce the sound correctly.”

As expected to most ESL teachers, T2 also demonstrated proper English sounds. *“In teaching speaking, I often advise them to use common words and then teach them how to pronounce it properly and correctly and then after that we go on to more. After teaching them the correct pronunciation of those common words, we proceed to English words frequently used in the academe,”* the teacher discussed. T4 also believes that learning by practicing is important, whether individually, in groups, or as a whole class, students should practice speaking in different social context.

Theme 3: Give Collaborative Activities

Activities where students collaborate are effective ways for them to practice their English speaking skills just like most of the ESL teachers do. T1 expressed, *“I give a lot of collaborative activities, where students would not even feel that they are asked to speak in English because speaking just becomes a natural thing. By doing that, teaching speaking would not be a difficult thing for the teachers, which is really rewarding.”*

T5 also find collaborative activities effective as she said, *“I find collaborative activities more effective because the students feel less pressured when they work as teams and could come up with better ideas.”* Other ESL teachers also give collaborative activities like in T2 and T5. T5 said that apart from discussion, collaborative activities can also be done in class. *“I usually gauge their ability to share their insights individually and in group and of course their ability to speak in public,”* the teacher noted.

Theme 4: Ask Students Oral Presentation

In every speaking class, oral presentations of students are expected. Students are usually given topics either individually or by group and present it orally. In doing this, the ESL teachers set standards and most of the time create rubrics in evaluating the performance of the students. For T1 she said that during oral presentations, *“I never allow students reading what is written in their PowerPoint [presentation]. That’s why PowerPoint or written output is not that important to me. What is more important is the oral presentation or how they express themselves using the English language.”*

T3 sometimes ask his students to make videos of some advertisements and then present it orally in class, which includes critiquing the advertisement, and discussing about the approach used in the advertisement. T2 also believes that oral presentation does not just practice their pronunciation or use the language, but it also helps them to be confident in speaking the English language.

When orally presenting to the class, T2 advises students that their visual aids or PowerPoint presentations should be simple and in brief so it would not be confusing for the class. T4 also believes that visual aids are important in oral presentations. She said that visual aids are required as the need arises. For example, in oral presentation, they may have PowerPoint presentation or poster if their topic requires.

Theme 5: Facilitate Fun Activities

In facilitating speaking activities to students, it is not only important they learn, but also better if students enjoy so they can learn with ease and look forward to learning more. There are varieties of fun activities that ESL teachers facilitate. For T4, this is what she does, during discussions, *“I usually ask students of their thoughts and opinions about our topic. Though it is not like a graded recitation, I see to it that most of them, if not all share their views by asking them directly. For example, after I discuss something, I will ask a question, and anybody can answer. If there are contradicting opinions or views and some of the students are dominating the discussion, I will ask one or two who haven’t had the chance to talk yet to choose which side he agrees with. This would ensure participation from everyone. I think that if students are not pressured to answer a question and be graded they will be more participative and active in speaking or reciting.”*

T1, however, usually starts her English class with a conversational English. The teacher demonstrated, *“It’s like a warm-up activity where you make students feel comfortable and prepared for the class. You do it by simply asking questions like how are they, how their mornings are, or if they are familiar with a particular national issue or news. Then I usually have ‘Speaker of the Day’. Every day, before the start of the class, a student is assigned to speak anything about he / she has read, watched, experienced, discovered or anything that the student wants to share in the class as long as he / she will speak.”*

For T2, she practices what she called as 3Cs. She said, *“In my oral communication class, I tell them to practice the 3Cs; the first is critical thinking, and then of course confidence, and then the conversational fluency.”* T4 also has a way of motivating students by usually asking students of their thoughts and opinions about the topic. She said, *“I see to it that most of them, if not all share their views by asking them directly. For example, after I discuss something, I will ask a question, and anybody can answer. If there are contradicting opinions or views and some of the students are dominating the discussion, I will ask one or two who have not had the chance to talk yet to choose which side he or she agrees with. This would ensure participation from everyone. I think with this, students are not pressured to answer a question and be graded. They will be more participative and active in speaking.”* For T2, T3, and T5, they also give speaking activities in a form of games.

Theme 6: Facilitate Simulation / Authentic Activities

What else could be done better to facilitate an activity that simulates life activities to prepare students in the real world. T3 believes that in conducting speaking activities, *“I consider how practical it is for them, how it will be practical for them to the next five or ten years as soon as they graduate the tertiary level of education.”* T3 facilitate debate activities from time to time, including interviews. He said, *“I find the activity effective because it was not common for them, but it is necessary to be socially skilled like that they can conduct themselves in situation that they can in a snap they could place their best foot forward.”*

However, T1 prefers to give authentic speaking activities like asking the students to bring realia or real life objects to demonstrate the procedure of a particular activity like bringing ingredients to demonstrate on how to prepare a menu or dessert and having spare parts to demonstrate on how to assemble a machine or object. Other activity that simulates reality is in the form of interview, which T1, T3, T4, and T5 also conducts. What T2 does is, *“I sent them outside for them to interview Filipino students and then they all came back telling me, ‘your students are very confident in speaking English,’ so I got confused when they told me about that and then what I realized is that when we instructors, when we talk to them in English our students, they are intimidated that’s why they don’t answer back in English. They don’t talk in English. But if there’s a person who will talk to them that they know they are better in English they might really talk in English.”*

In summary, the challenges that most ESL teachers face in teaching speaking are:

1. Difficulty in pronouncing English words properly
2. Limited vocabulary resulting to code switching
3. Lack of confidence caused by fear of mistakes
4. Millennial behavior

However, the strategies that ESL teachers usually implement in teaching speaking are:

1. Encourage students to speak English
2. Teaching speaking by modelling
3. Give collaborative activities
4. Ask students oral presentation
5. Facilitate fun activities
6. Facilitate simulation / authentic activities

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the data, most Filipino tertiary students or ESL learners lack confidence in speaking because they are intimidated by the fear of making mistakes in pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary while speaking. This lack of confidence is also caused by their limited vocabulary. Since they cannot think of equivalent English words for some Tagalog words, most of them do code switching or just translate their thoughts in Tagalog and then speak English only if they know. Since English is not the Filipinos' first language, pronouncing English words properly is always expected to be a major problem. Most of them, despite one-on-one teaching of pronunciation, still cannot produce the proper sounds of some English words, especially those letter sounds that do not belong in the Filipino alphabet, like /f/, /v/, and /th/. What makes the situation worse is the students' emerging behavior caused by the influence of technology. Since most of them can just freely express their opinions about anything through blogging or by just reading online articles, most of them boldly say that teachers should not insist on making them speak in English because, anyway, they are Filipinos. This could be one of the most difficult parts of motivating students like them, because most of them do not even want to try to speak English. That makes the role of ESL teachers more challenging.

However, in teaching speaking, specifically in the communication classes of some ESL teachers, it can be concluded that ESL teachers have already developed strategies on how to deal with the challenges of teaching speaking. The teachers agreed that they should encourage students to speak English by making them understand that expressing their thoughts orally is more important than the rules of grammar and proper pronunciation. Although they are important, students should be reminded that errors in speaking are allowed, and nobody should have criticized them because we all know that we are Filipinos and English is not our native language. That is why ESL teachers just invest in teaching speaking by modeling or demonstrating the proper American sounds through the vowels, consonants, stress, and intonations. Teachers should be the ones to speak English all the time, so the students will always get the feel of the environment in which the English language should be used. Most teachers use collaborative activities because it is a natural way of making students speak without the pressure of the rules. ESL teachers also provide challenging activities that prepare students for the real world once they graduate from tertiary education. Activities that simulate life activities are advisable, like interviews, oral presentations, debates, and demonstrations, where students learn more because they do the real thing. This is the concept of learning by doing today that has become known as "experiential learning" or "action learning," promoted by the theory of Dale's (1969) Cone of Experience. Then, aside from the challenging activities, ESL teachers also want the students to enjoy the classes by providing fun activities through games and stimulating activities.

Based from the conclusion drawn from the result of the analysis, the following are recommended by the researcher:

1. ESL teachers should further promote the use of the English language through institutionalized programs like the Speak English Movement. The Speak English Movement was already launched in the school last year, but due to a lack of proper leadership and management, the program was not successful because it was not given serious leadership support and proper evaluation.
2. The school administration should invest in facilities that would further enhance the speaking skills of the students. Although the school has a speech laboratory, the English proficiency program being used with the students taking English classes does not seem to be effective because of the lack of proper system management. The school should have used standardized English proficiency programs to be on par with other schools that have the same goal of producing students who are globally competitive in communication skills, specifically in speaking the English language.
3. The ESL teachers should do in-depth research on the performance of the Filipino ESL learners in the English classes, so teachers would be guided in producing appropriate learning materials

suited to the needs of the tertiary students who are soon graduating and preparing for the reality of life. The ESL teachers should do benchmarking activities to search for good practices from other institutions on how they deal with the challenge of producing orally competent students. Also, the present research has only a limited number of participants, and it is better to have a greater number of ESL teacher participants to make the study more credible.

References

- Arriola, J. L. (2002). Issues on English as a second language: The Philippine experience. *UNITAS*, 75(2), 223-243.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315750534_Issues_on_English_as_a_Second_language_The_Philippine_Experience
- Astudillo, J. C. C. (2019). *CALL: The impact of Cambridge LMS on the enhancement of English grammar proficiency at a B1 level in 12th grade EFL students at Sagrados Corazones high school in Cuenca* [Master's thesis]. Universidad de Cuenca.
<http://dspace.ucuenca.edu.ec/bitstream/123456789/32109/1/Tesis.pdf>
- Bachman, L. F., & Palmer, A. S. (1996). *Language testing in practice: Designing and developing useful language tests*. Oxford University Press.
- Bernard, H. R. (2017). *Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches* (6th ed.). Rowman & Littlefield Publishers.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>
- Burns, A., & Joyce, H. (1997). *Focus on speaking*. National Center for English Language Teaching and Research. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED411709>
- Bygate, M. (1998). Theoretical perspectives on speaking. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 18, 20-42. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190500003469>
- Bygate, M. (2001). Speaking. In R. Carter & D. Nunan (Eds.), *The Cambridge guide to teaching English to speakers of other languages* (pp. 14-20). Cambridge University Press.
- Cabigon, M. (2015, November). *State of English in the Philippines: Should we be concerned?* British Council. <https://www.britishcouncil.ph/teach/state-english-philippines-should-we-be-concerned-2>
- Chavez, A. (2014). *What Asia can learn from Philippines about English education*. HuffPost. https://www.huffpost.com/entry/what-asia-can-learn-from_b_4572991
- Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing. *Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), 1-47.
http://www.uefap.com/tefsp/bibliog/canale_swain.pdf
- Chomsky, N. (2006). *Language and mind* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Clarke, V., & Braun, V. (2018). Using thematic analysis in counselling and psychotherapy research: A critical reflection. *Counselling and Psychotherapy Research*, 18(2), 107-110. <https://doi.org/10.1002/capr.12165>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Ellis, R., & Shintani, N. (2014). *Exploring language pedagogy through second language acquisition research*. Routledge.
- Goh, C. C. M., & Burns, A. (2012). *Teaching speaking: A holistic approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Halcomb, E. J., & Davidson, P. M. (2006). Is verbatim transcription of interview data always necessary? *Applied Nursing Research*, 19(1), 38-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnr.2005.06.001>
- Hamid, M. O., Nguyen, H. T. M., & Baldauf Jr, R. B. (2013). Medium of instruction in Asia: Context, processes and outcomes. *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 14(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14664208.2013.792130>

- Hymes, D. (1972). On communicative competence. In J. B. Pride & J. Holmes (Eds.), *Sociolinguistics* (pp. 53-73). Penguin.
- Johnson, K. E. (2009). *Second language teacher education: A sociocultural perspective*. Routledge.
- Johnson, K. E., & Golombek, P. R. (2020). Informing and transforming language teacher education pedagogy. *Language Teaching Research*, 24(1), 116-127. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168818777539>
- Laws, K., & McLeod, R. (2004, July). Case study and grounded theory: Sharing some alternative qualitative research methodologies with systems professionals. In *Proceedings of the 22nd international conference of the systems dynamics society* (Vol. 78, pp. 1-25). Keble College. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Kevin-Laws-2/publication/255047567_Case_study_and_grounded_theory_Sharing_some_alternative_qualitative_research_methodologies_with_systems_professionals/links/5ad8294e458515c60f5893bc/Case-study-and-grounded-theory-Sharing-some-alternative-qualitative-research-methodologies-with-systems-professionals.pdf
- Lazaraton, A. (2014). Second language speaking. In D. M. Brinton, M. Celce-Murcia, & M. A. Snow (Eds.), *Teaching English as a second or foreign language* (4th ed.) (pp. 106-120). Heinle and Heinle.
- Leonen, J. N. (2018, February 16). *Inquiry into decline of English skill of PH students sought*. Philippine Daily Inquirer. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/969318/inquiry-into-decline-of-english-skill-of-ph-students-sought>
- Maguire, M., & Delahunt, B. (2017). Doing a thematic analysis: A practical, step-by-step guide for learning and teaching scholars. *All Ireland Journal of Higher Education*, 9(3). <https://ojs.aishe.org/index.php/aishe-j/article/view/335/553>
- Nunan, D. (1991). *Language teaching methodology: A textbook for teachers*. Prentice Hall International.
- Otanes, F. T. (1988). The state of English language teaching in the educational system today. In A. B. Gonzales (Ed.), *The role of English and its maintenance in the Philippines (The transcript, concensus and papers of the solidarity seminar on language and development)* (pp. 81-86). Solidaridad Publishing House.
- Pe-Pua, R., & Protacio-Marcelino, E. A. (2000). Sikolohiyang Pilipino (Filipino psychology): A legacy of Virgilio G. Enriquez. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 3(1), 49-71. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-839X.00054>
- Prator, C. (1950). *Language teaching in the Philippines: A report*. US Educational Foundation in the Philippines.
- Roller, M. R. (2017). *Rapport and reflection: The pivotal role of note taking in in-depth interview research*. Research Design Review. <https://researchdesignreview.com/2017/06/26/rapport-reflection-the-pivotal-role-of-note-taking-in-in-depth-interview-research/>
- Savignon, S. J. (2018). Communicative competence. *The TESOL encyclopedia of English language teaching*, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0047>
- Skehan, P. (1996). A framework for the implementation of task-based instruction. *Applied Linguistics*, 17(1), 38-62. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/17.1.38>
- Skehan, P. (1998). Task-based instruction. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 18, 268-286. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190500003585>